

Comparison of Cysticercosis Infection of Tapeworm among Inspected and Non-Inspected Porcine Group

Kyi Kyi Shein *

Abstract

A total of 45 domestic pigs (inspected) from Ywathargyi farm slaughter house, South Dagon Township and 34 from meat markets (non-inspected) were examined histopathologically. The study period lasted from 2004 to 2005. The aim of this study is to investigate the comparison of cysticercosis infection of Tapeworm among inspected and non-inspected of porcine group. Tissue samples were examined to histological procedures and using routine staining procedures. The present study was undertaken at Pathology Research Division (DMR, Lower Myanmar). Brain, muscles, lungs, intestine, bladder were used in this study. In inspected porcine group, 4.44% of the death larvae were observed in cysticercus. 2.94 % of non-inspected porcine group were indicated the cysticercosis infection. Normal and infected cysticercus of porcine groups were described and supported by photographs and discussed from cysticercosis infection perspectives.

Introduction

The tapeworms are parasitic worms of the class cestoda of the phylum Platyhelminthes. *Taenia solium* metacestodes causes cysticercosis in both humans and pigs. (Harold, 1964) Cysticercosis is an infection caused by the pork tapeworm, *Taenia solium*. Infection occurs when the tapeworm larvae enter the body and form cysticerci (cyst) (Chatterjee, 1976). Neurocysticercosis is caused when cysticerci are found in the brain. Cysticercosis infection is found most often in rural areas and developing countries with poor hygiene where pigs are allowed to roam freely and feed on human faeces. This allows the tapeworm infection to be completed and the cycle to continue. Man may be both the definitive and the intermediate host of *T. solium*, since man harbours either the adult worm or the cyst (Lea and Febiger, 1981).

The larval stage of *T.solium* is termed as cysticercus cellulosae (Runnell, Monlux and Monlux, 1965). The tapeworm has a life span of as much as 25 years inhabiting the small intestine of man (Harold and Brown, 1964). Cysticerci (larval Taeniidae) are relatively common in domestic herbivores and omnivores.

The *cysterci* of taenioid cestodes of man occur chiefly in swine and cattle. *Taenia solium* is also known as the armed tapeworm, solitary tapeworm and the measly tapeworm. The adult inhabits the intestinal tract of vertebrates and the larvae inhabit the tissues of the vertebrates and invertebrates. *T. solium* Linnaeus, 1758, occurs in the small intestine of man. *Taenia solium* causes two different diseases—taeniasis and cysticercosis. Taeniasis occurs when the adult tapeworm infects the human intestine. Cysticercosis develops when people (or pigs) eat food contaminated with taenia eggs. The eggs cross the digestive tract, enter the circulation, and lodge in the tissues (usually the brain or muscles). The terms cysticercus is now used as a general term for a type of tape worm larva (Whitlock, Lea and Febiger, 1960). Cysticercosis is the commonest parasitic disease to affect the central nervous system (CNS). According to the World Health Organization (1988), more than 2.5 million people worldwide are infected. Cysticercosis, a zoonosis which causes a great impact on animal and human health, is an important problem in several areas of the world, mainly in Latin America, African and Asian countries, where it is endemic. *Taenia solium* cysticercosis is now recognized as a major public health problem in most developing countries because of its association with seizures. The people of Myanmar are great consumers of pork. Most people however are unaware of inspecting the meat. Meat inspection is conducted in legalized slaughterhouse. Marketed pork

*Dr., Lecturer, Department of Zoology, Dagon University

may or may not be inspected. Considering this, pork samples from inspected and non-inspected areas are examined from the aspects of histology and parasitology.

Objectives

- To observe the histopathological study of cysticercosis in domestic pigs.
- To examine the histological features of various tissues and organs of domestic pigs.
- To compare the cysticercosis infection among inspected and non-inspected porcine group.

Materials and Methods

Study design

A field and laboratory based on histological study was conducted in domestic pigs of two different colours: black and white.

Study site

The study sites for this research are Ywathagyi farm slaughtered house, South Dagon Township and 4 different markets of Yangon Region: meat markets from North Okkalapa, South Okkalapa, Yankin and Kamayut Township. (Plate I)

Study population

Total of 45 domestic pigs (inspected) and 34 (non-inspected) were used. Brain, muscles, lungs intestine and the bladder of domestic pork samples were collected as experimental organs.

Study Methods

Tissues biopsies were fixed in 10% buffered formalin. Gross cutting of the specimens and tissue processing were done.

The paraffin embedded tissue blocks were cut using a based-sledged microtome to produce section of 3 micron thickness. The slides were stained with haematoxylin-eosin for histological examination. The detection of cysticercosis infection in pork tapeworm was made by histologic staining method. (Baker, 1958, Carlton, 1957, and Drury, 1957)

Results

A total of 45 domestic pigs from Ywathagyi farm slaughtered house (inspected) and 34 from meat markets (non-inspected) were carried out. The results indicated that out of 45 domestic pigs (inspected), 4.44 % of dead larvae in muscle tissues were observed in cysticercus. Slight hemorrhage and extensive necrosis in brain are noted (Plate II, A).

In microscopic feature of inspected porcine group, a mature cyst is an opalescent ellipsoidal body. The long axis of the cyst lies parallel with the muscle fibre. The cyst contains a fluid rich in salt and albuminous material. It can live for about 8 months in the flesh of pig (Plate II, B). Therefore cysticercus cellulosae has been found in larval stage of *T. solium*.

In this study, cysticercus was found between 7 months and 8 months of pigs muscles. Pathological lesions were found in 10 cases of female and 7 cases were male. The death of the larva was found in clouding of the internal fluid and gradual calcification of the bladder wall. In the muscles there is degeneration and atrophy in the immediate vicinity of the parasite (Plate II, C). Small bronchus occurs in lungs of porcine (Plate II, E). Brain, intestine and bladder show normally in microscopic examination (Plate II, D, F). The larval stage of *T. solium* developed in the muscles. Histologically these larvae were similar to human tissue.

A. Yawathagyi farm slaughter house

B. South Okkalapa Market

C. North Okkalapa Market

D. Yankin Market

E. Hledan Market (Kamayut)

Plate I. Study sites of porcine group

Out of 34 domestic pigs (non-inspected), 2.94 % of pork from South Okkalapa had feature of cysticercosis infection. The cyst was found in any muscle of the body. The growing cyst produced a foreign-body inflammatory reaction. Growing cyst found 7 months in the flesh of pigs (Plate III, A). Generally in non inspected pork samples, there are no cysticercosis infection in those pigs of North Okkalapa, Yankin and Kamayut Township markets (Plate III, B). Brain marked infiltration of vessels and perivascular space by lymphoid cells (Plate III, C).

In histological examination alveolar hemorrhage, little congestion and hemorrhage were seen in lungs (Plate III, D). The bladder appears normal microscopically (Plate III, E). Little inflammation and diffuse hemorrhage occurred in intestine (Plate III, F). Tiny hemorrhage although in few numbers were observed in brain. The lesions varies from mild reddening to severe hemorrhage.

The normal and cysticercosis infectious disease of abnormal photographs are found in Plate II and III. The larval stage of *T. solium* develop in the muscles of the pig.

Table 1. Experimental pigs based on Age and Sex (inspected)

Age (month)	Sex (no.)		Cases (no.)
	Male	Female	
6	2	4	6
7	3	-	3
8	-	7	7
9	5	2	7
10	6	6	12
12	3	2	5
14	3	2	5
Total	22	23	45

Table 2. Different types of Pathological Lesions

Organ	Gross Lesion	Cases (no.)	Sex
Brain	Little haemorrhage	1	F
	Extensive necrosis	1	F
	Little necrosis	1	F
Muscle	Severe infection	1	F
	Extensive necrosis	1	F
	Haemorrhage	2	F
	Swelling	1	M
Lung	Extensive necrosis	2	M
	Little congestion	1	F
	Swelling	2	M
Intestine	Swelling	2	F
	Little congestion	2	M
Bladder	No obvious Lesion	-	-
Total		17	F = 10 M = 7

Discussion

Pigs take a part in great impact on animal and public health significance. A total of 34 domestic pigs (non-inspected) from meat markets of some places in Yangon Division showed cysticercosis infection. In this study, out of 34 domestic pigs (non-inspected), 2.94 % had features of cysticercosis infection in muscle taken from South Okkalapa Township. The growing cyst produces a foreign-body inflammatory reaction. The cysts are found in any muscle of the body. Out of 45 domestic pigs, 4.44 % were found to be infected with cysticercus. Swelling and little congestion were observed in lungs and intestine. The shape of the cysticercus varies according to its location (Vet parasitology, 2002). The death of the larva is followed by a clouding of the internal fluid and by a gradual calcification of the bladderwall. From this result muscle tissue of pigs showed more infected than other tissue.

They may live in the pig for several years, but later they die and become calcified (David L. Gelding, 1965). The cysticerci are found chiefly in the muscles of the heart, tongue, forearm, thigh and neck but may also occur in many other parts of the body (Vet parasitology, 1998). In addition to poor sanitation, unhealthy pig rearing practices, low hygienic standards, unusual customs such as consumption of raw pork is an addition factor contribution to the spread of the disease in some communities of Asia. Human and animals infected with cysticercus parasite usually cause of human morbidity and mortality. The symptomatology depends on the site affected.

A. Transverse section of brain

B. Longitudinal Section of infected muscle

C. Calcification of the death larva of cysticercosis infection

D. Normal Intestine of pig

E. Cross section through a small bronchus of pig

F. Normal bladder

Plate II. Inspected porcine group

A. Infected Muscle with growing cyst

B. Normal muscles of pig

C. Brain marked infiltration of vessels and perivascular space

D. alveolar hemorrhage of lung

E. Normal bladder of pig in section

F. Little inflammation of intestine

Plate III. Non-inspected porcine group

Table 3. Experimental Pigs based on Age and Sex (non-inspected)

Age (month)	Sex (no.)		Cases (no.)
	Male	Female	
6	0	7	7
7	4	4	11
8	3	4	7
9	9	3	12
Total	16	18	34

Table 4. Different Types of Pathological Lesions

Organ	Gross lesion	Cases (no.)	Sex	
			Male	Female
Brain	Little hemorrhage	2	1	1
Muscle	Hemorrhage/ Little Hemorrhage	4	2	2
Lung	Hemorrhage	3	2	1
	Little congestion	2	0	2
Intestine	Little inflammation/ Swelling	3	1	2
Bladder	No. obvious lesions	-	-	-
	Total	14	6	8

To prevent cysticercosis and other disease causing germs, avoid eating raw or under cooked pork, don't eat meat of pigs that are likely to be infected with the tapeworm. According to meat inspection at Ywathagyi farm slaughter-house by the health and authorities and the meat was carefully-boiled cooked at least 100°C (within 2 hrs).

Conclusion

Histopathological study was done for 45 domestic pigs (inspected) and cysticercosis infection was observed in 4.44% of muscle tissue. Little infection was seen in lungs and intestine. Brain and bladder showed no cysticercosis infection. The muscle tissues of pigs were more infected than other tissues. Out of 34 domestic pigs (non-inspected), feature of cysticercosis was found in 2.94 % of the muscles. In this study, gross lesions found in Pigs tissue were not different between male and female. This study pointed out that human beings were infected with cysticercus in brain and it could be neurocysticercosis. In animals porcine and bovine the infection it could be cysticercosis. Pigs have been appeared to be a carrier of cysticercus and as such which represent a major source for the zoonotic transfer of cysticercosis infection to human beings. Cysticerci may be destroyed by freezing at 10°C for 5 days, heating above their normal death point of 57°C and pickling in 25 percent salt solution for 5 days. The most practical safeguard is to cook meat thoroughly until it has lost its normal colour. In addition, pigs should not run on free range where human excreta may be found and all persons concerned with pig-raising should be regularly examined and treated for tape worms. For control of cysticercosis, prevention of faecal contamination of soil, proper disposal of sewage and avoiding raw vegetables grown in polluted soil are useful measures. To minimize the risk of cysticercosis in pigs it is necessary to raise pigs in confinement. The vaccines of Praziquantel and metrifonate have been reported to be effective in cysticercosis.

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